

INNOVATIVE POTENTIAL OF ENTREPRENEURS AND INNOVATIVE STRATEGIC FUNCTION OF THE STATE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6963819>

Abstract: comprehensive support of innovation activities, the development of the national innovation system, the development of new mechanisms for the introduction of high-performance technologies and the accelerated development of priority areas of science and technology are among the most important areas of large-scale economic reforms carried out in our country.

Keywords: micro-innovations, innovative activity, scientists, designers, engineers, effective use.

If micro-innovations and improving innovations can be thought out and implemented at the initiative of an entrepreneur and at his expense, then fundamental and significant innovations that cause profound changes in the economy provide for interaction, cooperation of four main forces - the state, science, entrepreneurs and society. Each of these forces has its own interests, performs certain functions in this cooperation and should have its share of using additional benefits from innovation, the product of innovation. Innovative activity is the basis of entrepreneurial activity. The high title of entrepreneur is worthy only of a leader who is inclined to constantly search and apply innovations to achieve success in the competitive struggle of an organization or enterprise operating in a market economy. This is not fate and not a moral duty given to entrepreneurs from above. This is a serious vital necessity, which is commanded by the need to survive in a tough competitive struggle.

Innovativeness is the law of competition, a necessary characteristic of a market economy, the burden of which the ukuz review system is doomed to stagnation, displacement and destruction by others. When assessing the innovative potential of entrepreneurs of any form of ownership, it is necessary to clearly distinguish:

- incentives that encourage entrepreneurs to embark on a risky path of innovation;
- innovation opportunities for entrepreneurs;

- restrictions that restrain the innovative activity of entrepreneurs.

Usually, the incentives that encourage entrepreneurs to innovate are that they sell a better, more competitive and completely new product on the market or a more efficient new or modified techno 29 is not all. Successful innovations really bring profit and even additional profit (innovative quasi-rent). But this additional benefit lies on the way to an innovative threshold, which not everyone can overcome: high costs during the development of a new product and technology (unavoidable development costs, which are especially high in relation to the finished new product or technology).

At the same time, it is unknown how buyers of a new or improved product (product or service) will behave, how much the market will perceive it, whether the costs will pay off and whether the expectations of sales volume will be met. In addition, a new product may have serious drawbacks that cannot always be eliminated completely, and the expected effect may turn out to be a wonderful dream, an illusion. Therefore, an entrepreneur will have to measure seven, that is, think carefully before starting any new business. But there is a force that encourages an entrepreneur to take the risk of innovation in any case. This is the power of market competition.

Competition law forces entrepreneurs to pursue a risky innovative path in conditions of declining profits, loss of competitiveness and the risk of bankruptcy. The rule "if not me, then another" applies. The market is crowded with producers of goods and services who are fighting not only for market "niches", but also for consumer demand and trends. The one who keeps calm and gets tired of arguing, who will overtake in this competition, sooner or later will lose his place in the market and become an outcast. This risk threatens every entrepreneur, whether small or large business (including TNCs, such as large American or Italian corporations that have recently gone bankrupt, whose losses amount to billions of dollars). When dividing the ownership rights to the results of scientific and technical activities obtained at the expense of the state budget, it is inappropriate to assign separate ownership rights to such results to the state, to transfer their fate to officials for consideration. The proposal to grant these rights to performers free of charge (with the exception of inventions related to the security and defense of the country) about 30 seems more reasonable. This will contribute to the growth of initiative and responsibility of entrepreneurs in the innovative use of inventions and other results of scientific and technical activities. However, when introducing a new order, it is necessary to remember about the third and main partner - a creative person who

embodies his ideas in inventions and other results of scientific and technical activities.

Scientists, designers, engineers, other authors of new effective technical ideas and persons assisting in their implementation should receive a guaranteed share of profits and additional benefits arising from this. The State should also play an active role in protecting local intellectual property abroad. Currently, its significant share is transferred almost free of charge to TNCs and horija firms and brings them a lot of income. It is necessary to take into account the experience of India, which receives multibillion-dollar revenues from the export of programs and other intellectual products, from the development of offshore programming: information technology accounts for about 20% of the total volume of Indian exports. We are talking here about the knowledge society, which by its nature is innovative, humanistic - about the development of society during the formation of the noospheric post-industrial civilization and the revision of the role of the state in the economy. In such a society, both approaches to the role of the state in the economy, characteristic of a backward industrial civilization, are generally unacceptable.

The concept of unlimited domination of the state as the owner and manager of the main wealth in society, the main investor and innovator has shown its inefficiency in the conditions of rapid economic development, the violence of the bureaucratic and bureaucratic apparatus, unable to adequately respond to the challenges of the time. Intellectual product (inventions, utility models, industrial designs, breeding achievements, computer programs, integrated circuit topologies, data sets 31, etc.k.) we are talking about the effective use of the most important part of the country's wealth, regardless of whose initiative and by what means it was created. When evaluating and examining applications for inventions, the State patent office should select the most promising and effective ones from them and promote their use by enterprises of all forms of ownership in the creation of new products and technologies.

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